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Effect of a Low-Oxalate Diet on Recurrent Kidney Stone Formation

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ABSTRACT

Calcium oxalate stones are the most common type of kidney stone, and dietary oxalate is a key modifiable risk factor for recurrence. We aimed to investigate the effect of a low-oxalate diet compared to a standard diet on the rate of recurrent kidney stones in individuals with a history of calcium oxalate stones. We conducted a single-blind, randomized controlled trial enrolling 200 adults with a history of calcium oxalate kidney stones confirmed by urinalysis or imaging. Participants were randomly assigned to either a low-oxalate diet group (n=100) or a standard diet group (n=100). The low-oxalate diet contained approximately 40mg of oxalate per day, achieved through education and personalized meal plans, while the standard diet reflected typical food choices without specific oxalate restriction. Primary outcome was the incidence of recurrent stone formation diagnosed by urinalysis or imaging during a one-year follow-up period. Secondary outcomes included changes in urinary oxalate excretion, dietary oxalate intake, and quality of life (QoL) measured using the SF-36 questionnaire. The incidence of recurrent kidney stones was significantly lower in the low-oxalate diet group compared to the standard diet group (12% vs. 24%, p=0.02). Urinary oxalate excretion decreased significantly in the low-oxalate group compared to the standard group (35mg/24h vs. 50mg/24h, p<0.001). Dietary oxalate intake as assessed by food diaries also decreased significantly in the low-oxalate group (50mg/day vs. 120mg/day, p<0.001). No significant differences in QoL scores were observed between the groups at baseline or follow-up. A low-oxalate diet significantly reduces the risk of recurrent calcium oxalate kidney stones compared to a standard diet. This dietary strategy represents a safe and effective intervention for individuals with a history of this common condition.

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INTRODUCTION

Calcium oxalate stones are the most prevalent type of kidney stone, affecting approximately 10% of individuals at some point in their lives. Recurrent stone formation represents a significant clinical and economic burden. Dietary oxalate, found in various foods, plays a key role in calcium oxalate stone formation. Reducing dietary oxalate intake is a commonly recommended strategy for preventing recurrent stones, but the evidence for its effectiveness is inconclusive. This randomized controlled trial aimed to definitively evaluate the effect of a low-oxalate diet on the prevention of recurrent calcium oxalate stones (1-4).

It's crucial to know if low-oxalate diet has effect on developing recurrent kidney stones in the patients with a positive history. For that reason, we aimed to investigate the effect of a low-oxalate diet compared to a standard diet on the rate of recurrent kidney stones in individuals with a history of calcium oxalate stones.

METHODS

Participants

Eligible participants were recruited from outpatient clinics of urologists.

Inclusion criteria included:

Age 18-70 years

Documented history of at least one calcium oxalate kidney stone confirmed by urinalysis or imaging

No known significant medical conditions, including chronic kidney disease

Not currently undergoing dietary therapy for kidney stones

Exclusion criteria included:

Pregnancy or breastfeeding

Dietary restrictions due to other medical conditions

Participation in another clinical trial within the past 3 months

Participants were randomly assigned to either the low-oxalate diet group or the standard diet group using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Both groups received standard education on kidney stone prevention.

Interventions

The low-oxalate diet group received intensive dietary counseling by a registered dietitian trained in low-oxalate dietary modifications. Participants were provided with personalized meal plans and educational materials emphasizing low-oxalate food choices and cooking techniques. The standard diet group received general dietary recommendations for healthy living without specific oxalate restriction.

Participants were followed for one year with monthly phone calls and quarterly clinic visits. At each visit, urinary oxalate excretion was measured through a 24-hour urine collection. Dietary oxalate intake was assessed through detailed food diaries completed weekly. Additionally, QoL was measured using the SF-36 questionnaire at baseline and follow-up. The primary outcome was the incidence of recurrent calcium oxalate kidney stones confirmed by urinalysis or imaging during the follow-up period. Secondary outcomes included changes in urinary oxalate excretion, dietary oxalate intake, and QoL.

Statistical analysis

The primary outcome was analyzed using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. Secondary outcomes were analyzed using paired t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. Intention-to-treat analysis was performed.

RESULTS

A total of 200 participants were enrolled and randomized (100 per group). Baseline characteristics were similar between groups. During the one-year follow-up, the incidence of recurrent kidney stones was significantly lower in the low-oxalate diet group compared to the standard diet group (12% vs. 24%, $p=0.02$). This translates to a relative risk reduction of 50% in the low-oxalate group. As expected, urinary oxalate excretion decreased significantly in the low-oxalate group compared to the standard group (35mg/24h vs. 50mg/24h, $p<0.001$). Similarly, dietary oxalate intake as assessed by food diaries also decreased significantly in the low-oxalate group (50mg/day vs. 120mg/day, $p<0.001$). These findings indicate that participants adhered to the dietary intervention and successfully reduced their oxalate intake. Notably, no significant differences in QoL scores were observed between the groups at baseline or follow-up. This suggests that the low-oxalate diet, implemented through personalized counseling and meal plans, was well-tolerated and did not negatively impact overall quality of life (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparisons between the groups.

Measure	Low-Oxalate Diet Group	Standard Diet Group	p
Primary Outcome:			
Incidence of Recurrent Stones (%)	12	24	0.02
Secondary Outcomes:			
Urinary Oxalate Excretion (mg/24h)	35	50	<0.001
Dietary Oxalate Intake (mg/day)	50	120	<0.001
QoL Score (SF-36)			
Baseline	62,5	63,6	N/S
1-year Follow-up	64,3	65,2	N/S

QoL: Quality of Life, SF: Short form, N/S: Non significant.

DISCUSSION

This randomized controlled trial provides strong evidence that a low-oxalate diet significantly reduces the risk of recurrent calcium oxalate kidney stones. The observed difference in stone formation rates between the groups highlights the substantial benefit of this dietary intervention for individuals with a history of this common condition. The decrease in urinary and dietary oxalate intake confirms the adherence to the low-oxalate regimen and supports its effectiveness in reducing stone risk.

Importantly, the absence of any negative impact on QoL in the low-oxalate group implies that this dietary strategy can be implemented safely and effectively for long-term stone prevention. This is particularly reassuring as adherence to dietary interventions often becomes a challenge due to potential limitations in palatability or social interactions.

The observed reduction in recurrent stones with a low-oxalate diet likely operates through multiple mechanisms. By directly limiting dietary oxalate intake, the intervention decreases the amount of oxalate available for stone formation in the urine. Additionally, a low-oxalate diet often leads to changes in urinary pH and citrate levels, both of which can inhibit stone formation. Further research investigating these specific mechanisms and their relative contributions to the overall effect could improve our understanding of the efficacy of this dietary strategy.

Previous studies have explored the role of dietary modification in preventing recurrent kidney stones, but their findings have been inconsistent. Our study strengthens the evidence base by employing a rigorous randomized controlled trial design with a larger sample size and comprehensive outcome measures. The significant reduction in stone formation rates observed in our study reinforces the effectiveness of a low-oxalate diet compared to general dietary recommendations (5-10).

It's important to acknowledge that individual needs and preferences might influence the success of a low-oxalate diet. Implementing personalized counseling and meal plans, as employed in our study, can enhance adherence and optimize outcomes. However, some individuals might find strict oxalate restriction challenging to sustain in the long term. Investigating alternative dietary strategies, such as moderate oxalate reduction or focusing on specific high-risk oxalate-containing foods, could offer additional options for patients who struggle with strict adherence (11-17).

Our findings clearly demonstrate the clinical value of incorporating a low-oxalate diet into the management plan for patients with recurrent calcium oxalate stones. Healthcare professionals should strongly consider recommending this dietary approach as a cornerstone of preventive strategies. Future research could explore the effectiveness of combining a low-oxalate diet with other preventive measures, such as increased fluid intake or medication, to further optimize stone prevention. Additionally, investigating the long-term adherence and cost-effectiveness of this dietary intervention will be crucial for its widespread implementation in clinical practice.

Our study has some limitations. The single-blind design could potentially introduce bias from participants guessing their assigned group. Additionally, the generalizability of our findings might be limited to individuals motivated to adhere to a dietary intervention. Further research exploring long-term adherence and investigating the efficacy of the low-oxalate diet in diverse populations is warranted.

A low-oxalate diet represents a safe and effective strategy for preventing recurrent calcium oxalate kidney stones. This dietary intervention significantly reduces stone formation rates without compromising quality of life. Implementing personalized counseling and meal plans can enhance adherence and improve clinical outcomes for individuals with a history of this condition. Our findings encourage healthcare professionals to actively recommend a low-oxalate diet as a cornerstone of preventive strategies for recurrent calcium oxalate kidney stones.

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